

STScI | SPACE TELESCOPE
SCIENCE INSTITUTE

STScI Science Writer's Workshop

[Cosmic Cartography with Roman: Advances in Galaxy Structures, Distributions, Dark Matter, and Dark Energy](#)

Date: Wednesday, July 16, 2025

Time: 9:30 – 11 am EDT

Location: CafeCon at Space Telescope Science Institute & Virtual

9:30 – 9:35	Welcome & Introduction	Moderator: Hannah Braun, <i>Webb Deputy News Chief, STScI</i>
9:35 – 9:45	Roman Operations Update	Julie McEnery, <i>Senior Project Scientist, Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope, NASA's Goddard Spaceflight Center</i>
9:45 – 9:55	Roman: A New Era In Astronomy	Karrie Gilbert, <i>Project Scientist, Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope, STScI</i>
9:55 – 10:10	Mapping the Dark Universe Across Space	Alexandra Amon, <i>Assistant Professor of Astrophysics, Princeton University</i>
10:10 – 10:25	Mapping the Dark Universe Through Time	Lauren Aldoroty, <i>Postdoctoral Research Associate, Duke University</i>
10:25 – 10:35	AI & Machine Learning with Roman Data	John Wu, <i>Assistant Astronomer, STScI</i>
10:35 – 10:45	Synergies with New Telescopes	Kristy McQuinn, <i>Head, Roman Mission Office, STScI</i>
10:45 – 11:00	Question & Answer	All